

BUILDING A FUTURE: THE ROLE OF CULTURE IN NEW UZBEKISTAN'S IDEOSPHERE

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the issue of the development of the ideosphere of society in connection with cultural and educational growth. It is based on the fact that the cultural and educational development is carried out through the restoration of the population's worldview, way of thinking, historical heritage and traditions. In the ideosphere of New Uzbekistan's democratic society, it has been revealed that without strengthening the foundations of cultural advancement, it is impossible to achieve a new democratic mindset and way of thinking, as well as the development of a democratic society.

Keywords: ideosphere, philosophy, spirituality, democracy, society, science, education, culture, humanity, ideology, development.

Today, we are striving to acquire advanced scientific-innovative, technological, financial-economic, and political-legal knowledge, and to become familiar with the achievements of world culture, art, and literature. It is necessary to emphasize the importance of literature and reading culture. Regarding the development of the ideosphere of the society, great attention is paid to the development of the literature field along with all other fields in our country.

In fact, our democratic reforms, which are being carried out in order to increase the status and influence of the Uzbek language and literature at the state level, are gaining urgent importance in our country. For instance, On October 21, 2019, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's Decree "On measures to fundamentally increase the prestige and position of the Uzbek language as a state language" [1] was adopted, and a draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Language" was developed to ensure the implementation of this Decree. Also, the State Language Development Department [2] and Terminology Commission [3] were established under the Cabinet of Ministers. In particular, on August 10, 2020, the Department for the Development of the State Language announced the national competition titled "May your honor be high, my mother tongue". On April 10, 2020, the President adopted the Law of the Republic of

Uzbekistan “On Establishing the Day of the Uzbek Language Holiday” [4]. Accordingly, October 21 has been designated as “Uzbek Language Day” in our country. With this, it was reflected that our spiritual value - our mother tongue, which is one of the symbols of the state, which plays an important role in the development of the society’s ideosphere, is under the protection of the law. Today, the introduction of the position of adviser on spiritual and educational affairs and the state language for the heads of administrative offices and organizations in the state administration indicates that the position of our mother tongue is getting stronger in our country.

Today, in order to deliver the Uzbek language and literature, its philosophy to the people of science, in 2019, we can see the publication of volume VIII, which consists of the works of the great encyclopedist Abu Rayhan Beruni, “Harakatlanish yo’li”, “Zijlar yog’dusi” and “Xaritashunoslik” [5].

In 2019, UNESCO’s decision to celebrate the 1000th anniversary of Ibn Sina’s rare work “The Laws of Medicine” was an important innovation in our spiritual life. “The Laws of Medicine” is the world’s first scientific approach to the state of the healthy and unhealthy body. The role of this work in the formation and development of the ideosphere of society is incomparable, the celebration of the thousandth anniversary of this work is considered a symbol of the birth of scientific technology [6]. Ibn Sina’s unique creativity and rich spiritual heritage made a worthy contribution to the development of world science, and an international award of the UNESCO organization was established in the name of the scholar.

On the occasion of the 125th anniversary of the birth of Abdulla Qodiriy, one of the representatives of Jadid literature, the writer’s novel “O’tkan kunlar” was translated into English by British literary scholars and American translators in two countries for the global readership. This work was first translated from Uzbek into English by the famous American translator and researcher Mark Edward Reese and published in the USA under the name “Bygone Days”. It is also noteworthy that it is included in the catalog of the largest library of the United States - the Library of Congress. The preparation of this work in electronic book format also contributes to Uzbek literature securing its rightful place among world literature. The second English-language version of the novel, sponsored by the Islam Karimov Foundation and produced by British literary scholar Carol Yermakova, was published under the title “Days Gone By” by the renowned Nouveau Monde Editions in France [7]. The translation of such masterpieces into foreign languages, especially English, French, Korean, Russian, Chinese and

other languages, makes it possible for Uzbek literature to be recognized in the world community. Today, in our country, the best Uzbek works such as “Yulduzli tunlar”, “Humoyun va Akbar”, “Dunyoning ishlari”, “Shum bola”, “O’tmishdan ertaklar” have been translated into foreign languages and are about to be published.

In February 2020, the “Al-Furqan” Islamic Heritage Foundation of Great Britain donated about one hundred unique manuscripts and catalogs in Arabic, Turkish, and Persian languages that are kept in world funds to the Imam Bukhari International Research Center. It is noted that this manuscript, among others, provides valuable information about works held in libraries and manuscript collections in countries such as Burkina Faso and Côte d’Ivoire, as well as several European countries, through catalogs published in these regions. As a result, it opens the door of great opportunities for us to study and research the scientific and spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, to further increase their place and role in the ideosphere of society.

On the occasion of the 579th anniversary of Alisher Navoi’s birth, the prose version of the “Farhod and Shirin” epic from his work “Khamasa” was translated into English for the first time by translator Azam Obidov. It was published in Turkey and presented to readers.

Another development in our national literature is the translation of Abdulhamid Sulaymon o’g’li Cho’lpon’s novel “Night and Day” (“Kecha va Kunduz”) into English. The translation was completed by Christopher Fort, a lecturer in the Department of Slavic Languages and Literatures at the University of Michigan in the United States, and the book was published in November 2019. The presentation of the work took place on January 17, 2020 at the Embassy of Uzbekistan in London. In general, this novel is one of the important steps in the development of Uzbek literature.

On August 19, 2020, the establishment of the badge of Muhammad Aminkhoja Mukimi was an important event in our country. This badge is awarded to the winners of the contests “Best Poem”, “Best Art”, “Best Animation”, “Best Screenwriter”, “Best Online Platform Author” [8].

Today, on the basis of democratic spiritual renewal in the society’s ideosphere, the role of creative contests, festivals, and international creative cooperation in various directions is extremely important. It is worth noting that the national and international festivals held in our country enhance Uzbekistan’s spiritual and educational potential, improve its international image, expand spiritual and educational activities among youth, foster collaboration among

artistic groups, promote our national values, and provide participants and guests with an opportunity to become closely acquainted with our country's material and spiritual heritage.

In response to these needs, various festivals have been organized in our country, including the "International Handicrafts" Festival, the "International Circus" Arts Festival, the "Sharq Taronalari" International Music Festival, the "International Bakhshi" Arts Festival, the "Nurli Navolar" and "Great Silk Road" International Folklore Music Festivals, the "Silk and Spices" Festival, and the "Anor" Agrotourism Festival. These events are promoting Uzbekistan's spirituality, culture, and art to the world.

Today, the democratic innovations in the field of art express human interests, encompassing the impact of specific artworks on people's worldview and spiritual development, as well as the diverse processes involved in creating new artistic works imbued with fresh meanings influenced by these impacts.

In the process of spiritual renewal in the current society's ideosphere, the role of music is incomparable. Music is one of the factors that defines the national image of our people, inculcates good ideas and innocent feelings in the human heart. From this point of view, it should be noted that our nation has had a high musical potential since ancient times. The discovery of a bone musical instrument, a flute, from 3,300 years ago in the Urgut district of Samarkand region, along with the perspectives on musicology of our great ancestors such as Farabi, Ibn Sina, Navoi, and Babur, allows us to make such a conclusion [9].

At the initiative of the First President Islam Karimov, the "Sharq Taronalari" international music festival, which has been held in our country since 1997, embodies its own meaning and human interests. This festival, which serves to renew and enrich the unique musical traditions of the world's nations, and at the same time brings together various nations and peoples through art for common goals, demonstrates the validity of this conclusion.

Today's strategic reforms open the door to great opportunities for in-depth study of our unique musical heritage, development of the art of music, and passing it on to the younger generation.

The "1st International Handicrafts Festival", held in Kokand from September 10-15, 2019, played a significant role in showcasing the diverse Uzbek national handicrafts from 34 different fields by 1,116 artisans and 87 organizers from 153 districts of our republic. It was crucial in promoting its unique examples, developing tourism, and enhancing the societal ideosphere. In addition, the precious fragments of the national culture of our people are

included in the World List of the Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity of the United Nations Organization for Education, Science and Culture, UNESCO. In 2001, the Boysun cultural region, in 2003, “Shashmaqom”, and in 2009, the “Great Singing” of the Fergana Valley, as well as Navruz, which is considered an ancient holiday of various Eastern peoples, were included in UNESCO’s World Intangible Heritage List of Humanity. In 2010, the UN declared March 21 as the “International Day of Nowruz”. Currently, more than 7,500 objects of cultural heritage are registered in our country. Many of them are included in the UN World Cultural Heritage List. The Ichanqala complex of Khiva, the historical centers of Bukhara and Shahrisabz, the city of Samarkand are among them [10]. In 2016, Palov was included in the representative list of UNESCO.

In conclusion, the strategy for democratic spiritual renewal in the societal ideosphere is primarily related to a sincere understanding of our people’s history, cultural heritage, and the essence of national and universal values, as well as the wise use and development of these elements. So, without certain ideological factors, the political and social development of the society is impossible.

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